

CONTINUUM MODEL FOR GRAPHENE-BASED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Graphene has been attracting great interest because of its distinctive band structure and physical properties. The study of graphene-based composites is one of the most important aspects. In this paper, a coarse-grid (CG) beam model of graphene is proposed based on molecular structural mechanics approach and energy equivalence. The determination of the Young's modulus and geometrical parameters of the coarse grid of graphene are described. Then the continuum model for graphene-based composites is established to calculate the elastic properties of the composites. The covalent bonds between carbon atoms found in graphene are simplified to the coarse-grid model and assigned elastic properties using beam elements. The matrix phase is modeled as a continuum medium using solid elements. The connection of these two regions is assumed to be bonded perfectly. Analysis of graphene-based composites having single layer graphene with different coarse factors are performed. Using the proposed model, the deformations obtained from the simulation are used to predict the elastic moduli of the graphene-based composites. A significant enhancement in the stiffness of the graphene-based composites is observed. The finite element results are in an acceptable agreement.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene, a two-dimensional sheet composing of single-layered carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb lattice structure has drawn tremendous interest due to their excellent properties in many fields. Many researchers have pursued the analysis of graphene using different approaches, such as ab initio method and density functional theory, Monte Carlo simulations, and molecular dynamics. The amount of calculation makes the numerical simulation limited. The approaches based on continuum theory are used to describe the mechanical properties of graphene. Some equivalent models based on continuum mechanics are proposed to analyze the mechanical response of graphene. Odegard et al. [1] proposed a truss model, wherein the rods of different stiffness represent the stretching and in-plane bending capabilities of the C-C bonds. A molecular structural mechanics (MSM) approach was presented by Li et al. [2] to calculate effective elastic constants of graphene. The beam element is used to simulate C-C bond by establishing an energy equivalence. Xiao et al. [3] developed a modified MSM model to predict mechanical properties of defect-free graphene and carbon nanotubes. Georgantzinis et al. [4] used structural mechanics atomistic modeling in conjunction with spring-like finite elements to compute the elastic mechanical properties of graphene sheets. Alzebdeh [5] used atomistic finite element simulation in conjunction with a beam model to evaluate elastic constants for SLGSs with different size. Although the MSM approach or finite element method were widely used to

analyze the mechanical properties of graphene at atomistic scale in the past decade, their tremendous amount of computation is still the biggest obstacle for analysis of the graphene or other carbon nanostructures, especially the large-scale or multi-layered graphene and their composites.

Due to the extremely high tensile strength and elasticity modulus of graphene, the idea of using graphene as a reinforcement in a composite material is imposed as a logical step. Stankovich et al. [6] reported a general approach for the preparation of graphene-polymer composites, which provides a path to a broad new class of graphene-based materials and their use in a variety of applications. At present, lots of attention is paid on the synthesis and performance improvement of graphene-based composites. Due to the tiny size of graphene and the lack of basic information about graphene-based composites, it is still a great challenge to characterize the structure and manipulate the fabrication of these materials. Computer modeling and simulation method is used to overcome this conundrum. Xu et al. [7] investigated the structure and mechanical interactions at a graphene-metal interface through density functional theory-based calculations. It is helpful to understand the performance of the interfacial properties of graphene-metal composites. The influence of the chemical functionalization of graphene on the interfacial bonding characteristics between graphene and polymers was investigated using molecular mechanics and molecular dynamics simulations by Lv et al. [8]. However, the above works are time and size limited. Structural mechanics method becomes an important way to study the properties of nanocomposite material. Li et al. [9] examines the effect of interfacial load transfer on the stress distribution in carbon nanotube (CNT)/polymer composites using a multiscale modeling. The nanotube was modeled by the molecular structural mechanics method at the atomistic level. Jiang et al. [10] established the cohesive law for interfaces between a CNT and polymer characterized by the van der Waals force. The cohesive law was used by Tan et al. [11] who built a micromechanics model to predict the behavior of CNT-reinforced composite. The multi-scale representative volume element was used to modeling the behavior of CNT-reinforced composite by Tserpes et al. [12] and Joshi et al. [13]. Similarly, these method could be used for graphene-based composites. However, the tremendous amount of computation is the biggest obstacle for analysis of nanocomposites.

This paper presents a coarse-grid (CG) model to simulate single-layered graphene sheets based on molecular structural mechanics. And the CG model is used to build the model of graphene/polymer composites. The amount of calculation and time cost are reduced remarkably.

2 THE CG MODEL FOR GRAPHENE

Considering the geometric characteristic of a graphene, we use a coarse grid to replace the carbon atom-bond structure of a graphene sheet for reducing the computational scale. The coarse grid is a hexagon similar to atomic structures of the graphene. Each coarse grain stands for a virtual atom, and each side of the coarse grid represents a virtual bond between virtual atoms, as shown in Fig. 1. For simplification, the orientation of the coarse grid can be chosen as the same as the atom-bond structure of a graphene. Let L represent the bond length of carbon-carbon atom and L_n denote the side length of hexagons of coarse grid. It is assumed that $L_n = nL$, where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ is called as coarse factor. This means that a side of coarse hexagonal grid can cover n bonds of carbon atoms. For different coarse factor n we can obtain different CG models. Obviously, when $n = 1$, the CG model is the same as the original atomic structure of a graphene. There are n^2 hexagons formed by carbon-carbon bonds in each coarse hexagon for CG model with coarse factor n . Therefore, the coarse factor n is a key parameter for the CG model of a graphene, which is related to the specific size of coarse grids of a graphene. For instance, the coarse factor n is 3 for the case shown as Fig. 1, because a coarse hexagon covers 9 atom-bond hexagons.

Denoting strain energy of atom-bond structure of a graphene by U and strain energy of the coarse grid by U_n , the energy equivalence of two models leads to

$$U_n = U \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) can be used to determine the geometry and material parameters of the coarse hexagonal grid.

Figure 1: A CG model of a graphene (the coarse factor $n = 3$).

3 THE PARAMETER DETERMINATION OF CG MODEL

In order to calculate the energy of the graphene and its coarse grid, the MSM approach is used in the present work. The atom-bond system is modeled by a frame structure consisting of beam members in MSM approach. Each side of a coarse hexagon is treated as a prismatic beam element with a round cross section. The parameters of CG model can be determined by using energy equivalence between coarse grid and graphene. Undoubtedly, the size and scale of CG model depend on the coarse factor n . When $n = 1$, the coarse grid is exactly the same as original graphene.

The energy can be derived under a uniform stress field, as shown in Fig. 3. For this purpose, a unit cell is selected and the equivalent loads are obtained, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 2: Graphene subjected to tension loading.

Figure 3: A unit cell of graphene subjected to tension loading.

The strain energies of the unit cell due to bending and axial deformation can be developed as below:

$$U_{n-unit} = 3\sigma^2 t_n^2 L_n^5 / (16E_n \pi r_n^4) + 27\sigma^2 t_n^2 L_n^3 / (16E_n \pi r_n^2) \quad (2)$$

where t_n is the thickness of the coarse grid depending on the coarse factor. σ is uniform applied stress. E_n represent the Young's modulus of the beam. r_n is cross-section radius of the beam for the coarse grids.

When $n = 1$, the strain energy of the unit strut can be derived as:

$$U_{1-unit} = 3\sigma^2 t_1^2 L_1^5 / (16E_1 \pi r_1^4) + 27\sigma^2 t_1^2 L_1^3 / (16E_1 \pi r_1^2) \quad (3)$$

where t_1 is the thickness of the coarse grid with $n = 1$, which is equal to the thickness of graphene. E_1 and r_1 represent the Young's modulus and cross-section radius of the beam for coarse grids with $n = 1$. For convenience, it is assumed that all coarse grids have the uniform thickness and the same material properties. i.e., $t_n = t_1$, $E_n = E_1$ and $G_n = G_1$. G_n is shear moduli of beams for coarse grids. Eq.(1), we can deduce:

$$U_{n-unit} = n^2 U_{1-unit} \quad (4)$$

Combining Eqs. (1)-(4), we have a relation:

$$r_n^2 = (9nr_1^4 + nr_1^2 \sqrt{81r_1^4 + 4nL_1^4 + 36nL_1^2 r_1^2}) / (2L_1^2 + 18r_1^2) \quad (5)$$

For CG model with $n = 1$, i.e. the original graphene, the correlation between inter-atomic molecular potential energies and strain energies of a beam is established using the equivalence of energies, and the following relations can be obtained [2]:

$$r_1 = 2\sqrt{k_\theta / k_r}, \quad E_1 = k_r^2 L_1 / (4\pi k_\theta), \quad G_1 = k_r^2 k_\tau L_1 / (8\pi k_\theta^2) \quad (6)$$

Thus the geometrical and material parameters of beam for coarse grids are fully determined for the given coarse factor.

4 THE MODEL OF GRAPHENE-BASED COMPOSITES AND RESULTS

The CG model is used to build model of graphene-based composites. The graphene is modeled by beam elements while the matrix is simulated by solid elements. The surface of the matrix is full covered by the graphene, as shown in Fig.4. The graphene/matrix interface is assumed to be bonded perfectly. Consider a graphene with 240000 bonds to reinforce polymer matrix with Young's modulus 2.41GPa and Poisson ration 0.35. We can get different models of graphene reinforced polymer composites by setting different coarse factors. Here the coarse factor n is set to be 1, 2, ..., 10. The elastic deformation for these models can be calculated. Then the unidirection effective Young's modulus of the composite can be obtained. The effective Young's moduli and the number of elements used in these models are listed in Table 1 where the ratio E_{G_n} / E_{G_1} reflects the accuracy of results calculated by different models. It can be seen that the models with CG model of graphene can give accurate results for effective Young's modulus of composites. Even for the case of coarse factor $n = 10$, in which the element numbers used in CG model is reduced to 100 times of elements of graphene, the calculated effective Young's modulus is very precise. It is also found that a relatively smaller coarse factor n can generate the more accurate results. And all of the results are in an acceptable agreement. The calculation assumption of the model reduces significantly with the increase of coarse factor n . This is very valuable to the numerical computation of graphene-based composites.

Figure 4: Graphene/ polymer composite.

n	Effective Young's moduli (GPa)	E_{G_n} / E_{G_1}	Element numbers of graphene	Element numbers of matrix
1	46.752	1	240000	4431104
2	46.663	0.998	60000	1713776
3	46.611	0.997	26533	250339
4	46.516	0.995	15000	159810
5	46.425	0.993	9600	93039
6	46.063	0.985	6534	64249
7	45.958	0.983	4871	52270
8	45.962	0.983	3750	42263
9	45.903	0.982	2904	34852
10	45.696	0.977	2400	26997

Table 1: Results of models for graphene/polymer composites.

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